

Performance Precision: a Software Prototype for Computer-assisted Annotation and Analysis of Music Performance

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ABSTRACT

This software demo showcases an ongoing project developing an open-source application for analyzing recorded music performances. After loading an MEI score and an audio performance recording, the software can temporally align these two media and generate annotations automatically. The software can also align multiple performances to each other, beyond their shared score, making it easy to compare their interpretive nuances. Attendees may try the software on a provided laptop, or install it easily on their own computers. I anticipate this interactive experience will stimulate conversations about UI design, diverse use-case scenarios, and future functionality suggestions.

1. MOTIVATIONS

Music performance analysis often involves both performance recordings and score information, but the software tools available to performance researchers do not integrate these components, and their workflow remains cumbersome, often entailing manual data entry. Currently, music scholars concerned with annotating musical elements in recordings—such as downbeats, pitch, or note onsets (e.g., in [1, 2])—lack tools tailored for this task and must rely on general-purpose sound processing software. For example, a typical workflow for recording timestamps in *Sonic Visualiser* (SV) [3], arguably the most popular software among such music scholars, involves “tapping” beats manually on the user’s keyboard, as in [4]. A recent study in [5] reveals similar habits in users’ workflow.

To help address the software needs of performance researchers, this project introduces *Performance Precision*, an open-source software tool which integrates both scores and recordings with a graphical UI, designed to facilitate common workflows for performance analysis. Provided with a digital musical score and a performance thereof, *Performance Precision* can automatically generate meaningful annotations about note onsets and tempo, fully integrated with the score. The software displays and visualizes the score, the audio, and the selected annotations in intuitive ways designed to streamline performance analysis.

Audio-to-score alignment is a core task in Music Information Retrieval (MIR), and there is voluminous research on this topic, such as [6, 7, 8, 9]. However, its application

to music performance analysis has been underexplored despite its natural relevance. *Performance Precision* utilizes audio-to-score alignment technology to automatically detect the onset times of each note in the score; users can also correct and fine-tune the result on the software easily, with visual support. Therefore, this application can serve as an exemplar of how innovations from the interdisciplinary MIR community can be brought to scholars and musicians in the humanities.

2. FUNCTIONALITY DESIGN

The UI of *Performance Precision* is adapted from *Sonic Visualiser*, leveraging the existing SV user base and maintaining the software ecosystem. As shown in Figure 1, *Performance Precision* adds a panel on the left of the UI displaying a score, along with score-related controls underneath it. The score is internally rendered using Verovio [10] from a user-loaded MEI score file [11]. The panels on the right visualize loaded performance recordings in the form of spectrograms, while the bottom panel shows the tempo curve of the currently active recording. The installers and source code are published on GitHub at <https://github.com/yucongjiang/CAAMP>.

When a user triggers the audio-to-score alignment functionality, the program links the estimated timestamps of performed note onsets with the score times. By default, notes sharing the same score time (e.g., a chord) are assumed to share a single performed time. The results are represented visually: estimated timestamps are displayed as vertical lines on a spectrogram, each line with a score-time label nearby, and musical notes in the live playback are highlighted in real time with a marker on the score. Users can also click on a note on the score to jump to its (estimated) playback position. With this visual support, users can easily correct and fine-tune any misalignment by dragging the vertical lines.

Users can load multiple performance recordings of the same piece to compare interpretive nuances. Once all recordings are aligned to the score, users can switch playback from one to another seamlessly without interruptions in the score. To decrease the effort of correcting alignments in each additional recording, the program can “smart copy” already verified alignments from the first recording to subsequent recordings based on audio-to-audio alignment [12], generally more accurate than audio-to-score alignment.

The alignment results themselves are annotations about performance timing, and they can be exported to CSV files, with one column containing the score-time labels and the other containing the timestamps. Such alignment files can

Figure 1. User interface of *Performance Precision* (adapted from *Sonic Visualiser*), with three recordings loaded and aligned.

be imported back to the software, displaying previously determined note onsets on the spectrogram. User can add panes and data layers, and export any additional annotations, just as in *SV*.

3. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Inherently, *Performance Precision* can deal with only notated music. At this early stage, its annotations are focused on timing, but additional aspects such as dynamics and articulations are being considered for the future. As an ongoing project, this tool will benefit both from input from prospective users and from technical advancements made by MIR researchers. I also envision this tool working together with other relevant software applications, forming a software ecosystem in terms of standardizing data formatting for interoperability. Overall, *Performance Precision* has the potential to serve as a platform bridging multiple research communities including MIR, MEI, and music performance studies.

Acknowledgments

This project is supported by a grant from the National Endowment for the Humanities. Special thanks to Chris Canam for his invaluable technical support.

4. REFERENCES

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